

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.20681273

Heavy Metals Concentration In Some Processed Canned Fish And Beef And Their Toxicological Effect On Humans

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ABSTRACT

The increasing global consumption of products from canned foods due to its easy accessibility have raised much concern on heavy metals contamination resulting in health risks due to its gradual bioaccumulate in the body which finally becomes poisonous to the system. This study was conducted to determine the concentrations of some of these heavy metals in commonly consumed canned fish and beef products. Nine different products consisting of three canned sardines, three canned mackerel and three corned beef products commonly consumed in Warri metropolis were sampled. Heavy metals of concern were cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr), copper (Cu), nickel (Ni), lead (Pb), zinc (Zn), manganese (Mn), cobalt (Co) and iron (Fe). Samples were routinely collected, processed and digested in accordance with USEPA Method 3050B. Digested samples were determined using atomic absorption spectrophotometric method. Most of the values obtained complied with WHO/FAO and NESREA standards. Values obtained for six of the metals; Cd (<.001 - .017ppm), Cr (<.001 - .015ppm), Cu (.024 - .072ppm), Fe (.817 – 1.802ppm), Mn (.002 - .093ppm) and Zn (.23 – 1.18ppm) were below permissible limits, while Ni values fluctuate, while all Pb values were above the maximum permissible limits, with canned sardines having .45 - .79ppm, canned mackerels .45 - .64ppm and conned beefs .15 - .59ppm. The values obtained for Co were also high and affected were two sardines (.102 and .103ppm), two conned beefs (.157 and .275ppm) and two canned mackerels (.423 and .445ppm). The findings highlight critical food safety concerns regarding canned food products in the Nigerian markets and underscore the need for enhanced regulatory monitoring, improved quality control in food processing, and enforcement of best international safety standards. Consumer awareness programmes and dietary diversity recommendations are essential to minimize heavy metals exposure risks and bioaccumulation.

Keywords: Canned fish, Corned beef, Heavy metals, Bioaccumulation

INTRODUCTION

Survival is always associated with unforeseen situations. Daily activities such as working, thinking, associating and other aspects must be accomplished by feeding the stomach, else no tangible outcome. Therefore human survival depends on sustaining the stomach at all time. That is why availability of food must sometimes be accomplished by the eating of processed food. In this class are steel metal lacquered canned foods such as sardines, beefs, cooked cereals and many others. This also involve the use of aluminum foils and other methods of food preservation. For years, this method of preservation has

become means of making food get to various destination. This method is very important in the life of some group of people as means of survival. Hence this has created avenues for heavy metals to appear in the food chain of most affluent and vulnerable despite pollution of the water body from which fishes are obtained for onward processing for various markets (Peretiemo-Clarke *et al.*, 2009; Balogun *et al.* 2024). For instance, the military when at war. During the first world war of 1914 - 1918 and the second world war of 1939 to 1945; food items were packed using protected or lacquered canned metals for soldiers going to war front, this include bully beef or corned beef, tinned stew and tinned fish (D'Acquisto, 2026). Since then, it has become a practice. Today, it has become means of showing how affluent one is because this is now common in most supermarkets all over the world. Most of these containers become wounded or dented in the process of transportation and carriage and as a result, the lacquered container become corroded and eventually contaminate the food items. This end up releasing some of these metals into the processed food item, most of which are heavy metals; thereby creating health risk. Heavy metals contamination in food has become a source of concern because of diseases associated with them due to gradual bioaccumulation and biochemical conversions in the body (Rubio *et al.*, 2018).

The consumption of canned food products has increased significantly worldwide due to their convenience, long shelf life, and relatively low cost. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), global production of canned foods exceeds 30 million tons annually (FAO, 2023). However, this widespread consumption raises concerns about potential health hazards associated with these products, particularly regarding the presence of heavy metals.

Canned foods typically involve metal containers made from tin-coated steel or aluminum, with protective internal linings. During processing, storage, and distribution, various chemical reactions can occur between the food contents, container materials, and environmental factors (Kumar *et al.*, 2022). These interactions potentially facilitate the migration of heavy metals from packaging materials into food products.

Several studies have documented the presence of heavy metals such as lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), mercury (Hg) and arsenic (As) in canned food products (Russo *et al.*, 2021). These metals can accumulate in the human body through dietary intake and pose significant health risks due to their toxicity, persistence and bioaccumulative properties. The World Health Organization (WHO) has established maximum permissible limits for heavy metals in foods, yet compliance varies globally, and monitoring systems differ in effectiveness across regions (WHO, 2022).

The source of these heavy metals in canned foods can be multifaceted. Some originate from environmental pollution affecting the raw food ingredients such as the source of the sea food from which there may be some level of industrial activities, transportation from which there may be spillage and other infractions; while others may result from manufacturing processes, including the soldering of cans, corrosion of container materials, or contamination during processing (Ukulu *et al.*, 2019; Järup, 2019).

In developing countries, where regulatory oversight may be less stringent, the risk of heavy metals contamination in canned foods presents a particular concern. Limited infrastructure for quality control and testing, combined with economic pressures to reduce production costs, can result in the use of lower-quality materials and processes (Balogun *et al.*, 2024).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection

Samples were obtained from three major markets located in Warri metropolis. They were Edjeba market, located in the South Eastern part of Warri South Local Government Area with the following coordinate: Lat. 5.54043°N, Long. 5.74164°E. Ekpan market, which is located in the North Eastern part of Uvwie Local Government Area with the following coordinate: Lat. 5.5658°N, Long. 5.7421°E; and Ogborikoko market which is also located in Uvwie Local Government Area, but in the North Western part. The coordinate of the market is: Lat. 5.54144°N and Long. 5.763325°E. To purchase these canned food, the focus was on those that are commonly consumed and are always available in these markets. In all nine samples were investigated, involving three canned sardines, three canned mackerel and three corned beef.

The samples were coded and analyses were based on this coding. The essence of coding was to avoid controversy and litigation.

Sample Preparation

Samples were prepared using USEPA Method 3050B as a guide (USEPA 1996; Radojevic & Bashkin, 1999). From each sample, about 10 gm were collected into a Petri dish from each container using clean plastic spoon in order to avoid contamination. Each samples was dried in Memmert U30 over at 105°C for about 5 – 6 hours to remove oil, moisture and concentrate each into a dry component. The dry samples were then grinded into flacks or powdery form. This ensures easy digestion in the subsequent procedures. From each dry powdery sample, 1 gm was weighed into a 250 ml flat-bottom flask in accordance with modified USEPA Method 5030B procedure. To the sample was added some drops of deionized water to make the sample wet. To was followed by the addition of 10.00cm³ of hydrofluoric acid (HF); 5.00cm³ of trioxonitrate (V) acid (HNO₃) and 1.00cm³ of perchloric acid (HClO₄) to each sample and gently stirred to ensure homogeneity. The contents were then covered with aluminum foil to prevent any metal escape from the mixture. This was heated to almost dryness over an electric hot plate at 95°C ± 5°C for about 1 hour. Where complete digestion was not achieved, the procedure (HF-HNO₃-HClO₄ mixture) was repeated until complete digestion (Clear solution) was attained. To each clear sample was added 10cm³ of 4M hydrochloric acid (HCl) and further heated for about 5-10 mins to further ensure complete digestion and homogeneity. The samples were allowed to cool to room temperature and filtered using Whatman 42 filter paper. The filtrate were then diluted to 100cm³ with distilled water with the aid of standard measuring cylinder. These samples were labelled appropriately and sent for quantitative analyses using atomic absorption spectrophotometric method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: WHO/FAO and NESREA Maximum Permissible Limits for Some Heavy Metals in Processed Beef and Fish (mg/kg)

Metal →	Cd	Co	Cr	Cu	Fe	Hg	Mn	Ni	Pb	Zn
Fish (WHO/FAO)	0.05	1	0.5	0.05	100	0.05	1	0.3	0.2	10
Beef (WHO/FAO)	0.05	0.1	0.1	5	50	0.03	1	0.2	0.1	50
Fish (NESREA)	0.05	1	0.5	3	50	0.5	1	0.3	0.5	50
Beef (NESREA)	0.05	0.1	0.1	4	40	0.03	2	0.2	0.1	40

Table 2: Quantitative Values Obtained for Heavy Metals in Processed Beef and Fish (mg/kg)

SN	Sample	Cd	Cr	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn	Mn	Co	Fe
	Code									
1	SS1	<0.001	0.007	0.049	0.096	0.454	0.851	0.003	0.103	0.817
2	SS2	<0.001	0.006	0.072	0.133	0.773	0.616	0.047	0.056	1.029
3	SS3	<0.001	0.008	0.065	0.075	0.785	0.856	0.047	0.102	1.115
4	GS1	0.004	0.01	0.044	0.256	0.454	0.656	0.066	0.423	1.802
5	GS2	0.015	0.006	0.067	0.194	0.643	0.234	0.01	0.037	0.799
6	GS3	0.017	0.015	0.059	0.272	0.565	0.574	0.067	0.445	1.759
7	CBS1	0.006	<0.001	0.042	0.102	0.574	0.526	0.093	0.157	0.972
8	CBS2	<0.001	<0.001	0.024	0.06	0.15	1.173	0.002	<0.001	0.934
9	CBS3	0.007	<0.001	0.045	0.75	0.59	1.18	0.085	0.275	0.985

Based on the outcome of the analyses, it was observed that most of the results obtained comply with WHO/FAO and NESREA standards while some did not. Values obtained for six of the metals; Cd (<.001 - .017ppm), Cr (<.001 - .015ppm), Cu (.024 - .072ppm), Fe (.817 – 1.802ppm), Mn (.002 - .093ppm) and Zn (.23 – 1.18ppm) were below permissible limits. Values obtained for all the nine samples for Pb were all above the maximum permissible limits. This is even worst for canned sardines (.45 - .79ppm) as against values obtained for canned mackerels (.45 - .64) and conned beefs (.15 - .59ppm). The values obtained for Co were also high. This affected two of the sardines (.102 and .103ppm), two of the beefs (.157 - .275ppm) and two of the canned mackerels (.423 - .445ppm). The values for the mackerel were excessive compare to other groups. Results obtained for Ni were all okay for canned sardines, while they are reasonably okay for other groups; however two samples of mackerel (.26 and .27ppm) and one of conned beef (.75ppm) were within the permissible limit range.

This shows that there is the need to watch the consumption of these canned foods so as to minimize the incidence of bioaccumulation in the body. The results obtained for all the samples were generally okay, except for few which involve two samples of sardines with high Co and Pb; two samples of geishas and beefs with high Co, Ni and Pb. On the whole, the values obtained for all the samples were reasonable. Generally, the values obtained for Cd, Cr, Cu, Mn, Fe and Zn were okay; while Co, Ni and Pb requires some level of control. Despite the fact that human activities such as transportation, using of chemicals to kill fish and industrial activities affected heavy metals concentration in fishes; as for beefs, the reason for these higher concentration are likely to be because they are agrarian animals, hence the source of their food can be a major factor that determines the heavy metals accumulation. The grasses on which these cows fed are sometimes treated with chemicals for the purpose of preservation, killing of germs and good growth. Some of these chemicals gradually becomes accumulated in the body of these cows before they are killed and processed for the markets.

These elevated values in heavy metals in these processed foods can be minimized by taking various precautions such as reducing human activities on the river, ban the use of chemicals in killing fish and having good legislation to check human activities. While for beefs, this can be controlled by ensuring that the animals do not graze on chemically treated grasses, the area where these grazing takes place should be kept clean and no chemical of any nature such as herbicides or pesticides are sprayed there. There should an alternative means of taking care of their health and growth. Finally, the quality checks of the containers should be verified by outside quality control body periodically so as to ensure that safety rules are strictly followed. All these are required to prevent food poison to those who consume them after processing, so as to prevent disaster to consumers in the future.

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